

MATLAB: A Game Changer in Mathematical Education

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ABSTRACT

Mathematics is universally recognized as the language of science. To describe any scientific or engineering phenomena, Mathematics plays an important role. Traditionally, mathematics has been taught through the conventional chalk-and-talk approach. While convenient, this method poses challenges in terms of visualization and handling complex computations. MATLAB is a powerful tool to overcome these issues. This paper presents a model for the effective integration of technology into the learning experience of a large and diverse group of students in first-semester B.E Course. MATLAB was incorporated into the curriculum and mathematical concepts delivered in class were practically demonstrated using MATLAB. At the end of the semester, student feedback was collected. These aspects are discussed in detail in this paper. The findings of this study provide insights for institutions intending to establish a Mathematics laboratory.

KEYWORDS: Chalk and talk; Curriculum; MATLAB.

INTRODUCTION

Buzz Aldrin once remarked, “For the future, primarily, we must educate people in science, engineering, technology, and mathematics.” His words underscore the fact that the progress of society and the universe at large is deeply dependent on these disciplines. As educators in engineering institutions, we bear the responsibility of integrating science and technology with mathematics in our teaching practices.

Although mathematics is widely acknowledged as the language of science, the manner in which it is typically taught often fails to reflect this reality. Many students perceive mathematics as a difficult subject, and one of the primary reasons is the lack of effective visualization in conventional chalk-and-talk methods. For instance, when the function $f(x) = \sin x$ is merely defined as a periodic function, students may not grasp its true meaning without visual representation.

Another concern is the limited discussion of real-world applications in mathematics classrooms. Topics such as integration are often taught procedurally, without highlighting their practical relevance. We believe that the introduction of any new concept should begin with its applications, as this approach naturally fosters curiosity and engagement among students.

Due to the absence of visualization and contextualization, students often fail to appreciate the true essence of the subject. Engineering students, in particular, must be adept at visualizing concepts and applying scientific knowledge within their respective domains. Unfortunately, many continue to struggle in precisely these areas.

The series of papers by Felder[1, 2, 3, 4] et al., suggests that more than 50% of the students are visual learners, which means they will understand the topic through visual mode. due to all these reasons, we strongly feel that the idea of delivering mathematics subjects needs to be

updated with various activities, usage of advanced tools along with the traditional teaching method.

There are many free/paid tools like MAPLE, R-Software, Python, MATLAB, Geogebra etc., through which we can deliver Mathematics lectures effectively through visualization [5]. Though all these tools have their own unique features and strengths, MATLAB stands tall with its unlimited features and constant up gradation in every interval of time [6,7].

The first MATLAB (the name is short for “Matrix Laboratory”) was not a programming language. Written in Fortran in the late 1970s, it was a simple interactive matrix calculator built on top of about a dozen subroutines from the LINPACK and EISPACK matrix software libraries. There were only 71 reserved words and built-in functions. It could be extended only by modifying the Fortran source code and recompiling it. The programming language appeared in 1984 when MATLAB became a commercial product. The calculator was reimplemented in C and significantly enhanced with the addition of user functions, toolboxes, and graphics. It was available initially on the IBM PC and clones; versions for Unix workstations and the Apple Macintosh soon followed. In addition to the matrix functions from the calculator, the 1984 MATLAB included fast Fourier transforms (FFT). The Control System Toolbox appeared in 1985 and the Signal Processing Toolbox in 1987. Built-in support for the numerical solution of ordinary differential equations also appeared in 1987. The first significant new data structure, the sparse matrix, was introduced in 1992. The Image Processing Toolbox and the Symbolic Math Toolbox were both introduced in 1993. Several new data types and data structures, including single precision floating point, various integer and logical types, cell arrays, structures, and objects were introduced in the late 1990s. Enhancements to the MATLAB computing environment have dominated development in recent years. Included are extensions to the desktop, major enhancements to the object and graphics systems, support for parallel computing and GPUs, and the “Live Editor”, which combines programs, descriptive text, output and graphics into a single interactive, formatted document. Today there are many toolboxes , providing extended capabilities in specialized technical fields [8].

Soon after getting autonomous status to our institution, we had a privilege to prepare the curriculum. Being a teacher of Mathematics, the first thing coming to our mind is to teach mathematics effectively using advanced tools to our students, so that students will be able to understand the concept easily and consequently they will get interest in the subject. Correspondingly we prepared the curriculum and in each module we included experiential learning through the MATLAB tool. Fortunately, our institution has purchased an annual subscription with unlimited license.

The process of adoption of MATLAB to First semester BE students, process of execution is elaborated in the next section. At the end of the semester, we collected the feedback from a set of students, and the result was analyzed and discussed.

Based on teachers' experience, students' feedback, we are planning to make a few changes in the coming semester. Possible changes and other relevant concerns were also discussed in the article.

RESEARCH / PRACTICE ELABORATIONS

When we began framing the curriculum for first semester BE students, we made sure that each module should contain application oriented problems and experiential learning the corresponding concept through MATLAB. As per the University norms, we included 05 Modules namely Differential Calculus, Linear Algebra, Vector Differentiation, Calculus and Differential Equations. Corresponding to these curriculums, we framed 08 lab experiments as follows:

Expt 01: Introduction to MATLAB

Expt 02: Basic Matrix Operations

Expt 03: Plotting the Graph and Partial differentiation

Expt 04: Linear Algebra

Expt 05: Vector Differentiation

Expt 06: Calculus

Expt 07: Ordinary Differential Equations

Expt 08: Applications of Differential Equations (Newton's Law of cooling graph is shown in Fig. 1)

When we framed the experiments, we had the following challenges. But, fortunately we are able to resolve it with the help of Management and the department faculty members.

Fig 1. Newton's Law of cooling

Training for Teachers: As we were teaching only in the traditional chalk-talk method in the classroom, this method of teaching through Software is a new thing to all of us. Many of the faculty members are not familiar with the MATLAB software. This was the first challenge we have faced. To overcome that, we conducted a series of workshops to enhance their knowledge on MATLAB. As the MATLAB tools are user friendly, all of them learnt without facing much difficulties. At the end of the workshop, many of them gave constructive suggestions to improve the quality of experiments. This feedback helped a lot to set up experiments.

Lab Setup: Another major challenge was to set up the lab. In the first Semester, roughly we have around 600 students with 10 sections. Which means, in each section we have around 60 students. When we were setting up the lab we had two options, either to set the lab for 60 students or to divide the students into two batches., so that we could set up the lab with 30 computers. But, due to time table setup and other constraints we decided to set up the lab for 60 students. The management is generously provided all the necessary funds to establish the lab. Since we already had an institution subscription for MATLAB, we didn't face any difficulty in installing the MATLAB tool for the systems. Initially, we thought of conducting MATLAB sessions through Online portal (<https://matlab.mathworks.com/>), but as students did not have institutional mail ID at the beginning of the semester, we dropped the plan and decided to conduct the session through installed software. Once the system and software was ready, we made other arrangements like projector, board, racks to keep records. The lab instructor has been provided by the management for the smooth conduction of the lab.

Lab manual preparation: Though we had a good idea of the contents to be delivered in MATLAB sessions, we need to provide a Lab manual with appropriate contents, examples to students. Once we finalize the set of experiments to be discussed in the lab, a team of faculty members has been made to prepare the lab manual. They have done tremendous work and come up with beautiful Manual. In each experiment, we included Lab number, Experiment Name, Introduction for the topic, MATLAB Code with output, its application. At the end of each concept, we included a few Tasks/Exercises, which students had to perform during the Lab session. We also included the answers of each Task/Exercise, so that students can verify the answers.

Procedure to conduct labs: Once Lab is setup, manual is ready, the challenge was for the execution of plan. As we are getting 06 hours per week for Maths class, we split into 04+02. We kept 04 hours for regular class and remaining 02 hours (continuous) for the MATLAB session. The department has assigned two faculty members for each session, one faculty will be the main in-charge (the one, who is engaging regular class for that particular section) and one Co staff along with Lab instructor.

Procedure to Conduct exams and distribution of marks: In the Autonomous curriculum, 50 marks are assigned for the end semester exam and remaining 50 marks for Internal Assessment Marks (IA). Out of 50 IA marks, 30 marks awarded for 3 Internal tests. Hence, we decided to award a total of 20 marks for MATLAB sessions. Out of 20 marks, we planned to conduct two lab exams (after 04 experiment I test and at the end II test) for 10 marks each and average has to be considered. Remaining 10 marks, we awarded 05 marks for viva during the exam and 05 marks for the record book.

With all these challenges and with high expectations, we started our sessions. To maintain discipline and cleanliness in the lab, we come up with following rules and regulations in the lab as follows:

1. The session will be conducted for all the students of a particular section in one stretch, on the specified time. There will be no separate batches within the section.
2. The lab duration is 2 hours
3. Students are required to leave the footwear outside the lab. Wearing the footwear in the lab is strictly prohibited.
4. There will be an individual computer for all the students, if there are any issues then sharing option can be given (maximum of 2 students for one system).
5. The MATLAB tool is already installed on all the computers. Students are required to use the same. One system is exclusively kept for faculty and it is connected to a projector. Faculty members are requested to use the same.
6. Students are not allowed to access the internet. If there are any such instances, students need to take the permission of the faculty in charge.
7. In the beginning of the session, faculty in charge / Co faculty are required to explain the particular program and instruct the students to write the same in their observation book.
8. Once they complete the writing in the observation book, students need to execute the same in their respective computer.
9. All the programs will be performed in live script.
10. After the completion of the program, students need to save the program with proper file name and show it to concerned faculty.
11. The faculty may ask a few questions during verification. After the satisfactory completion, faculty in charge / Co faculty is required to put a signature in the observation book.

12. Kindly note that, a total of 20 marks is exclusively kept for the MATLAB session. Out of 20 marks, 10 for test, 05 for record and remaining 05 for student performance in regular labs (which includes viva, attendance and activeness in the lab). Please give
13. Record and student performance will be evaluated in all the sessions (it should be reflected in record book) and at the end of the semester, the average of all the sessions will be considered. Two tests will be conducted for 10 marks each (first test after 04 labs and second test at the end) and it will be proportionally reduced to 10 at the end of the semester.
14. As some tools/programs may take a little bit extra time, inform the students not to press the button more than once. Otherwise, the system may get struck.
15. Any issues related to computers, students are required to inform the lab instructor.
16. At the end of the session, instruct the students to delete the programs saved on the computer (if any).
17. If the student completes all the process early, executes all programs before specified time, they need to write the record in the lab itself.
18. Students are required to write observations in the assignment book (when it is ready) provided from the college.
19. Students are expected to bring the mathematics notes along with observation and record books.
20. If any student is absent for any of the labs, he/she has to complete the pending lab in the next session.
21. Students are solely responsible for the observation and record book. If it is misplaced, marks are proportionately reduced.

In the initial stage, there was some confusion with the proceedings during lab sessions. After several labs, we had some uniformity among us. The main staff will be explaining the relevant topic on the board, meanwhile co-staff will execute it in the MATLAB. This process will be completed within 25 to 30 minutes. Soon after that, students need to start executing exercise problems. The staff will be helping the staff during the execution. Once the execution part is done, students need to write the INPUT and OUTPUT in the observation book and get the signature of the staff. While coming for the next lab, students need to submit the record of the previous experiment. This process went on well, without any major issues.

Procedure for conducting the exam: As per our earlier decision, we conducted our first lab test after 04 experiments and Second test after the completion of all experiments. Since, in each class we have around 60 students, we decided to have three faculty members for the conduction of the exam. We prepared two sets of question papers to avoid copying from neighboring students. After the distribution of Question paper, students need to write the INPUT on the answer sheet and they were supposed to show it to the invigilator. Once they get the signature for INPUT, they need to execute the same in MATLAB. After execution, again they need to show it to the invigilator and after verification, students were supposed to submit the answer sheet. Meantime, students will ask for a viva and depending on their performance, marks will be awarded. At the end of the session, students will be awarded with a maximum of 20 marks. The same procedure will be followed in the second test and the average of two test marks will be considered as their final MATLAB assessment marks.

RESULTS

We asked the students about their opinion of introducing the MATLAB laboratory. Following is the questionnaire.

1. What is your opinion on Mathematics?
2. Which of the following methods are used by your Math teacher during PUC Classes?
3. Is the Inclusion of MATLAB in your BE Curriculum a good move?
4. Due to the Inclusion of MATLAB, what are your perspectives on the subject?
5. What is your overall rating about the inclusion of MATLAB?
6. Suggestion for Improvement in MATLAB in the coming days

We received 88 responses. Analysis of the response is given below:

What is your opinion on Mathematics Subject?

88 responses

Which of the following methods are used by your Maths teacher during PUC Classes

88 responses

Is the Inclusion of MATLAB in your BE Curriculum is a good move?
88 responses

Due to the Inclusion of MATLAB, what are your perspectives on the subject?
88 responses

What is your overall rating about inclusion of MATLAB
88 responses

Suggestion for Improvement in MATLAB in the coming days:

- It's a good idea to create matlab as we understood the importance of mathematics tools or any of the formulas.
- More than one session should be conducted every week
- MATLAB is very helpful to understand concepts!!! Thank you
- Good
- I am happy with the way it is present right now
- It's interesting
- Number of sessions should be increased so that we get to learn more things

From the responses we can make the following conclusions:

1. Most of the students learnt Mathematics in chalk and talk method (95%). Very few students said that they learnt mathematical software in PUC (18%).
2. 69% of students said that mathematics is interesting and easy.
3. Students also opine that inclusion of MATLAB is a good movement and it is helping them to understand math better.

From the responses we can easily conclude that students are enjoying MATLAB.

CONCLUSIONS AND SCOPE FOR FUTURE WORK

We are extremely delighted with our initiative towards a new teaching-learning methodology in Mathematics education for the current generation of technical students. We strongly believe that many institutions will come forward to introduce such types of initiative in their institutions. As we were introduced for the first time, we too had faced a lot of challenges but at the end of the day it is a much needed process for our students and they liked it very much, which was clearly visible in the feedback.

There are some institutions that have already introduced MATLAB/Maxima/Sci labs in their curriculum. The matter of concern is, students will lose their interest in Mathematics and they will concentrate more on the programming part. This issue needs to be handled in a systematic way.

With this experience, we are planning to continue the MATLAB sessions in the second semester too. As per the suggestions from the faculty members, we are planning to following changes for the qualitative sessions:

- i.** As there were 60+ students in each lab, handling the students with two faculty members is quite tedious. So HOD decided to allot three members for each session.
- ii.** In the first semester lab manual, we have not included the Aim/Objectives of each experiment. This time we felt, it's appropriate to include Aim/Objectives, which gives clear cut ideas for students.
- iii.** Many students suggested to reduce writing part during lab sessions. This suggestion looks reasonable, so we decided to reduce the writing part. Students need to write only Task Input and final output, no intermediate steps.
- iv.** We also decided to improve the quality of the lab manual, by including appropriate definitions, applications etc.

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